

Supporting Information

Nanoscale Imaging and Control of hexagonal Boron-Nitride Single Photon Emitters by a Resonant Nano-antenna

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METHODS

Preparation of hBN Defects. hBN flakes are exfoliated directly with Scotch tape on top of quartz substrate, or dry transferred on top of pre-patterned nano-antennas following a dry transfer method. The dry transfer involves the exfoliation of hBN flakes on polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamps, and a subsequent transfer onto the target substrate with the antennas. The use of quartz allows high temperature treatment of the materials and provides a one order of magnitude lower fluorescence background compared to normal glass coverslips. To induce defects into the hBN flakes, the samples are exposed to Oxygen and Argon plasma etching (with respectively 150 and 80 W power for 2 minutes).¹⁹ The samples are then thermally treated for 30 minutes at 850 °C in Argon atmosphere to stabilize the defects. Overall this process provides thin hBN flakes (<10 nm) with a high density of stable hBN emitters.^{16,30}

Antenna preparation. The antenna material, size and aspect ratio are designed in order to act as $\lambda/2$ dipole nanoantennas, with a tunable resonance. The antennas are fabricated at the apex of a tapered optical fiber. The fiber is used as a support for the antenna, which is

scanned in close proximity of the sample surface allowing the near-field interaction with the emitters. The antenna is fabricated out of a thin layer of aluminum deposited at the apex of the fiber, by means of Ga⁺ focused-ion-beam-milling (FIB). This reliable and reproducible method allows the fabrication of nanoantennas as scanning probes with a specific 3D orientation. The antennas are fabricated with a length of 160 nm and lateral size of 50x50 nm² with resonance at 620 nm wavelength. The orientation is flat or tilted of 30° with respect to the horizontal plane. A detailed description of the flat antennas fabrication procedure can be found in reference.²³

Scanning Antenna Microscope. The experiments were performed with a custom-built near-field microscope. It consists of an inverted confocal microscope, with a scanning probe head. The system allows the independent scanning of both the probe and the sample by means of a shear-force feedback mechanism. It allows keeping the probe at a constant distance of approximately 10-20 nm from the sample surface. This way the near-field coupling between the antenna and the emitter located in the hBN flake is permitted, with nanometer precision. Two main scanning configurations are possible: the probe can be scanned over an emitter continuously illuminated inside the diffraction-limited spot, or the sample can be scanned with the probe located in close proximity of the surface centered on the diffraction-limited spot.

The emitters are illuminated with light of 520 and 620 nm wavelength, focused using a 100x 1.3 NA oil immersion objective. Since the actual orientation of the antenna at the end of the probe is unknown, the system is excited with circular polarization. The laser power before the objective is 150 μW for the measurements in Figure 1 and 20 μW for all the other measurements, in order to prevent the melting of the antenna. Those values correspond respectively to energy densities of 300 and 40 kW/cm². Under these conditions, the hBN defects remained active for several months.

In collection path, long pass filters are used in order to separate the reflected excitation light. The fluorescence is confocally imaged onto two fast avalanche photodiodes (APD) (PD-050-COD, Micro Photon Devices) for single-photon counting and photon correlation. The collected light can also be sent to a custom-built spectrometer. In the spectrum is detected by means of an electron-multiplying charge-coupled device (EM-CCD) (Image EM x2 EM-CCD Camera C9-100-23B, Hamamatsu). The spectra integration time in figures 1b and 2e is 200 ms.

Photon Time-Gating Imaging and Lifetime Maps. The hBN defects are excited with a picosecond pulsed tunable laser ($\lambda = 520$ or 620 nm, pulse width ~ 70 and 30 ps respectively, SuperK Extreme, NKT Photonics), with 80 MHz repetition rate for data showed in figure 1 and 40 MHz for all the other cases. The use of time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) correlator (PicoHarp 300, PicoQuant GmbH) allows the recording of the absolute arrival time of the emitted photons on the APDs, with respect to the excitation pulse with 8 ps resolution. The instrument response function is of ~ 200 ps full-width half-maximum for light of a wavelength of 520 nm. Customized software allows the synchronization of this equipment with the scanning antenna microscope, in order to obtain intensity maps with photons histograms recorded at every pixel.

With subsequent data analysis it is possible to obtain intensity images integrating the photons at every pixel in specific time ranges, hence producing time-gated images, as shown in Figure 3 (b) and (c). Since the luminescence of the antenna is limited only to the first 2 ns, this technique allows the separation of the photons emitted by the metallic antenna and the hBN defect. Once that the emitter photons have been isolated by time-gating, a single exponential fit of the photons histograms at every pixel allows the generation of lifetime maps, as shown in Figure 3 (a).

Second-Order Cross-Correlation Measurements. We use a Hanbury-Brown-Twiss setup for second-order photon autocorrelation. The signal is split $50/50$ on to two APDs both with a time response of 200 ps at a wavelength of 520 nm. The photon arrival times on the APDs are cross-correlated, revealing the photon second-order autocorrelation of the hBN defects, and proving their single-photon emission behavior, as shown in Figure 1 (e). The correlation histograms are recorded with a bin size of 8 ps and later binned at 64 ps.

Numerical Simulations. We solve Maxwell's equations using a finite-difference time domain (FDTD) commercial solver (Lumerical Solutions, Inc., Vancouver). In general the hBN layer has been modeled as a 5 nm thick material with a refractive index $n = 2.2$.^{25,26} The dipolar antenna has been modeled as an aluminum nanorod of 160 or $140 \times 50 \times 50$ nm.

In order to quantify the excitation enhancement in Figure 5(b) and 6 (b), the total electric field intensity $|E_{tot}|^2$ across the antenna and the hBN layer has been calculated by FDTD. The given values have been normalized to the incoming total electric field intensity $|E_{inc}|^2$. Both, the excitation field and the one scattered by the antenna are simulated.

In Figure 5 (b) the source has been modeled as a circularly polarized one. In Figure 6 (b) the source has been modeled as a linearly polarized one, because the orientation of the antenna in X-Y plane would be known by fabrication and the polarization of the excitation beam might be easily aligned with it.

In Figure 5(b) the antenna is modeled as an aluminum nanorod of 160x50x50 nm, located 20 nm from the hBN layer. In Figure 6 (b) the antenna is located directly on a 5 nm thick hBN layer. This red shifts the resonance, and in order to have a dipolar antenna resonant at 620 nm, its length has been reduced to a size of 140x50x50 nm.

For the simulations of rates and lifetime profiles presented in Figure 5 the antenna has been located at 20 nm from the hBN layer. The emitter is simulated as a dipole emitter with internal quantum efficiency $\eta = 1$ and it is located inside the hBN layer, below the antenna. The emitter is modeled as a dipole oriented in X, Z and approximately isotropic. The latter emitter has been obtained combining the emission of three perpendicularly oriented emitters.

For the lifetime profiles the total power radiated by the emitter alone and the one of the emitter located in every specific configuration with respect to the antenna are compared. The ratio between the two powers is the reduction of lifetime at each antenna-emitter position.

The radiative and non-radiative rates shown in figure 5 are simulated in a similar way, taking into account that the light absorbed by the metallic antenna constitutes the non-radiative rate, while the light radiated in the far-field represents the radiative one.

The QEs reported in Figure 5 have been obtained placing the emitters at 25, 15 and 3 nm distance from the antenna. The values have been obtained with the following relation $QE = \frac{\eta_{rad}}{\eta_{rad} + \eta_{non-rad}}$, where η_{rad} and $\eta_{non-rad}$ are respectively the radiative and non-radiative rates.